

Ayushman Bharat-National Health Protection Mission a way towards Universal Health Cover by reaching the bottom of the pyramid to be a game changer or non-starter

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Abstract: Affordable and quality healthcare has not reached the majority of Indians after 70 years of independence. Only 25 % of the Indian population is insured under both private health insurance and government-run insurance schemes. To address this, issue the government had set up a High Level Expert Group in the year 2010 under 12 Th Five Year plan, which submitted its report with a focus on Universal Health cover as a basic component for social security. Recently Union Budget 2018 came up with Ayushman Bharat Programme that plans to cover 10 crore BPL families under a Health Insurance scheme. The paper attempts to look at various challenges to be faced in the implementation of this scheme and the role of various stakeholders required for its success.

Keywords: Ayushman Bharat, Health Insurance, Healthcare, National Health Protection Mission, NHPM, India

Introduction

The government’s world over commit to looking after the health of its people, to protect the real wealth of their nation, and ensure healthcare is accessible and affordable to all citizens alike. India too announced the biggest ever government-funded scheme of its kind in the world on Feb 1, 2018, which seeks to cover nearly 40% of its population called Ayushman Bharat- National Health Protection Mission on Feb 1, 2018.

Table A: Ayushman Bharat Scheme - Timeline of key announcements to date

Subject	Press Release	Date
Ayushman Bharat Scheme announced in Budget 2018-19	pib.nic.in/newsite/PrintRelease.aspx?relid=176049	Feb 1, 2018
Cabinet approves Ayushman Bharat – NHPM	pib.nic.in/newsite/PrintRelease.aspx?relid=177816	Mar 21, 2018
20 States sign MOU’s for implementing Ayushman Bharat	pib.nic.in/PressRelease.aspx?PRID=1535533	Jun 14, 2018
Launch of empanelment process for hospitals	Through Web portal http://www.abnhpm.gov.in	July 4, 2018
Use of Aadhar Desirable not Must in Ayushman Bharat	pib.nic.in/newsite/PrintRelease.aspx?relid=18052	July 12, 2018

The key stakeholders in the scheme besides the consumers or beneficiaries are the Healthcare Providers, state governments, and Insurance companies without whose support and involvement the execution of this scheme cannot happen.

The basis of inclusion in the scheme would those householders falling under deprivation criteria as per the Socio-Economic Caste Census of 2011 (SECC database 2011). It offers the benefits as under to its consumers.

TABLE B: Coverages for Beneficiaries

Coverages for Beneficiaries
A. Cashless Treatment at Public/Private Healthcare Providers
B. Secondary and Tertiary care hospitalization treatments Coverage
C. 5 Lakhs cover per family
D. No cap on the size of family or age of family members
E. Pre Existing Diseases covered from Day 1 of enrolment of the scheme
F. Pre and Post hospitalization expenses covered
G. Portable across India at all empanelled Healthcare Providers
H. Fixed Transportation Allowance payable from the place of residence to Hospital
I. AYUSH (Alternative Medicine Systems other than Allopathy) covered

Besides the objective of providing financial security through Universal health cover. The government also plans to set up 1.5 lakh health and wellness centres to provide primary healthcare facilities accessible to its citizens under the AB-NHPM programme.

Meeting the objectives and Issues in implementation

Low Public Spending on Healthcare and High Out of Pocket Expenses

Public spending on health in India (centre and state governments put together) has been in the range of 1.01- 1.3% of the GDP between 2008 and 2015 and was 1.4% in 2016-17 against the average of 6%. globally. Out of pocket expenditure out of total expenditure done by citizens themselves in India is nearly 70%, which is very high in comparison with countries world over.

Figure 1: Out of Pocket Expenditure on Healthcare by Providers (2013-2014) percentage

Source: Household Health Expenditures in India, (2013-14) December | 2016 National Health Accounts, Technical Secretariat. National Health Systems Resource Centre, Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India

As is clear from an analysis of the bifurcation of expenses above. 51% of the healthcare expenses, which are out of pocket, go towards OPD (Out Patient Treatment). Therefore, reduction in OOPE, which is an objective of the scheme, cannot only be met by health insurance, which covers in patient treatment or hospitalization expenses.

Dependence on Private Healthcare

It is clear from Table C: The majority of the Indian Population relies upon and prefers Private health care providers.

TABLE C: Hospitalization and type of Hospitals

Type of Hospital	Rural Area			Urban Area		
	1995-96	2004	2016	1995-96	2004	2014
Public	42	42	42	43	38	32
Private	56	58	58	57	62	68
Total	100	100	100	100	100	100

Source: 71st National Sample Survey (NSS) January-June 2014.

The scheme provides for automatic empanelment of public hospitals or government-run hospitals. The beneficiaries would not like to opt or prefer public/government hospitals for their treatments. The scheme provides for fixed rates or package rates for specific treatments and surgeries.

Further private hospitals will be happier to treat customers from outside the scheme as they can charge more than fixed package rates from them. The poor scheme beneficiaries might remain second priority or second class citizens for private health providers under the scheme.

Poor Existing Healthcare Infrastructure in India

India has just over one million allopathic doctors to treat its population of 1.3 billion

India has a bed to patient ratio of 0.9 per 1000 population.

We are creating demand for healthcare services by this scheme but there is not enough supply in terms of health infrastructure to cope with the demand.

Position of States as financier to the scheme

AB – NHPM scheme is to be implemented as a partnership of central government and states with 40% of the scheme to be funded by states and balance by the central government

Figure 2: Gross Fiscal Deficit Indian States 2006-2017

Source: State Finances a Study of Budgets of 2016-17, Reserve Bank of India. Ujwal Discom Assurance Yojana (UDAY) scheme. Under the scheme, states took over 75 percent of Discom debt between years 2015-17

As per the Reserve Bank of India (RBI), India’s central bank “The Gross Fiscal Deficit GFD-GDP ratio in 2015-16 went above the 3% ceiling of fiscal prudence for the first time since 2004-05.” States are resorting to large-scale borrowings. Besides farm loan waivers in some states, states own pay commissions increasing salaries of its employees, and uncertainty over GST revenues pose further downside risk as per RBI.

Inadequate Funds allocated for setting up Health and Wellness Centres (HWC’s)

The scheme envisages setting up and upgrading 1.5 lakh, HWC’s centres to cater to the medical treatment need of its centres. 1200 crores have been allocated under the scheme for the purpose. The amount is grossly inadequate for the number of centres it seeks to establish.

Rejection of the scheme by certain states

20 States have already signed up to administer the scheme in their states. States with existing schemes of their own will have either to converge their schemes into AB-NHPM or subsume the scheme afresh.

West Bengal, Karnataka, Orissa have kept out of the scheme and plan to have their scheme. What is common among these states is the party at the centre does not rule these states. Going forward there is a possibility of opposition parties winning in other states and rejecting the scheme. This will hamper the success of the programme.

Empanelment of Private Hospitals under the scheme

In a bid to standardize procedures for treatments the government has come up with a fixed package for 1350 procedures/ medical treatments and surgeries. Already the private healthcare providers have raised concern about these being very low. This according to them is unsustainable in the short and long term and would compromise on the quality of services for recipients. High medical inflation of 15% will make these packages unviable in times to come if not revised regularly.

Enrolling private hospitals in the scheme would be a challenge for the government.

However, the government’s argument is these package rates are for treatment in general ward category rooms only so are adequate to cover the procedure.

Besides this government is offering an incentive to increase the cost by a certain percentage in the following cases

TABLE D: Incentives to Raise Fixed Package Rates

Cause	Incentive %
NABH Accredited Hospitals (Entry Level)	10%
NABH Accredited Hospitals (Advanced)	15%
Location 115 identified backward/rural districts	10%
Healthcare Providers with Training colleges	10%

States have been given further flexibility of increasing this by 10 %.

Private hospitals to succeed profitably under the scheme have to change their business model or strategy from the existing model of a low or modest volume of business with high margins of profit to the new model of high volumes of business and low margins of profit. Will the private be willing to change their existing business models is to be seen. Also, most of the big private hospital chains are corporatized and publically held with shareholders influencing the decisions, to migrate to a new business model of doing business will be difficult.

Discovery of Premium through Tendering Process

Though the government has also clarified that there will be no limit on premiums and the same will be discovered through the tender process. The Insurer with the lowest bid will be selected state wise. Further, each state will have a different premium depending on the total population of the state and profile of the population. The state of Chhattisgarh is the first state in India so far to release the tender for the scheme.

This might lead to unhealthy competition and there might be price discovery at unhealthy rates leading to non-continuation by the insurer after a year. . It is to be seen how the private and public insurers respond to the tenders.

Faulty Coverage's proposed in the scheme

By covering pre-existing diseases from Day one and putting no cap on the age of beneficiaries, the government through the scheme features has prepared a dangerous cocktail to swallow for the insurance companies. This will be a high-risk pool of participants, which are bound to increase the loss ratios of private insurers affecting their profitability. Considering the fact, the earlier schemes of low-cost life insurance and personal accident insurance Pradhan Mantri Jeevan Jyoti and Suraksha Bima Yojna respectively have an upper age limit of 55 years and 70 years respectively.

High Loss Ratios of government-sponsored Schemes

Government-sponsored schemes in India are generally plagued by very high loss ratios and high claims. Net Incurred Claims Ratio (ICR), which is the ratio of net claims incurred to the net premium earned is an important ratio to gauge claim incidence and quantum.

TABLE E: Class wise Health Insurance -Net Incurred Claims Ratio – (2013-17)

CLASS OF BUSINESS	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15	2015-16	2016-17
Government Sponsored Schemes including RSBY	87%	93%	108%	109%	122%

Source: IRDA Annual Report 2016-17

The numbers above in Table E and Table F for government-run schemes paint a sorry picture, which will not entuse many private insurers to participate initially. Even if they participate initially to test, the waters there is a danger of withdrawal in case they are unable to contain the loss ratios in the future.

**TABLE F: Health Insurance (Excluding Travel-Domestic/Overseas & Personal Accident Insurance)
Incurred Claims Ratio (2016-17) - Non-Life Insurers**

INSURER	Government-Run Schemes including RSBY		
	Net Earned Premium	Claims Incurred (Net)	Incurred Claims Ratio (Net) 2016-17
Bajaj Allianz	1666	1607	96%
Bharti AXA			
CHOLA MS	0.00	-0.53	0%
Future Generali	1022	437	43%
HDFC ERGO			
ICICI Lombard	23939	32284	135%
IFFCO Tokio	7939	6016	76%
Kotak General			
Liberty Videocon			
L&T General	-0.5	0.0	0%
Magma HDI			
Raheja QBE			
Reliance	3075	2666	87%
Royal Sundaram			
SBI General			
Shriram General			
Tata AIG	167	418	250%
Universal Sampo			
Private Total	37808	43428	115%
National	80046	101305	127%
New India	84626	110243	130%
Oriental	3333	1820	55%
United India	62761	72535	116%
Public Total	230766	285903	124%
Aditya Birla			
Apollo Munich	0.00	1.90	0%
Cigna TTK			
Max Bupa	213	445	210%
Religare	483	873	181%
Star Health	1773	35	2%
Stand-alone Health Insurers Total	2469	1355	55%
Grand Total	271043	330686	122%

Source: IRDAI - HANDBOOK ON INDIAN INSURANCE STATISTICS – TABLE No. 79

Experience of Rashtriya Swasthya Bima Yojna (RSBY)

RSBY has been the only scheme in India launched on a Pan India basis, which aimed at Universal Health Coverage. RSBY offered a paltry sum insured of INR 30000/- for a family of 5 people. It involved the participation of the centre and states, the use of technology for the administration of the scheme, and involved participation of private sector hospitals and insurers. The centre and rest by states funded 75% of the insurance premium. Ayushman Bharat is somewhat comparable on many features though the amount of coverage and number of beneficiaries cannot be compared. The experience with unscrupulous private hospitals has not been good under RSBY. Private hospitals did systemic fraud by showing fake records of patient admissions under the scheme and claiming such amounts. Patients never received any treatment except on paper. Further, they gave giving unnecessary and unwanted treatment to patients to utilize the amount. With the level of corruption in India, there is no guarantee the unscrupulous private hospitals will not do the same this time with Ayushman Bharat–Scheme. The only action which was taken under RSBY was to de empanel the hospital. However, this is not enough to stops frauds like these from occurring again. Unless a strong deterrent of canceling the license of such wrongdoers and framing criminal cases against the promoters of such healthcare providers is brought, such operators will abuse the scheme. There is no agency set up under the scheme to monitor such wrongdoings.

Conclusion

This ambitious programme will disrupt the existing ways of working in the healthcare industry and create demand for healthcare services at an unprecedented level than the nation has seen before. The government has provided no answers on how the resources for the scheme will be generated. The budgetary impact of the scheme will increase the fiscal deficit in case revenues to meet the increased expenditure are not found. The scheme looks only at the demand of healthcare services, the supply side needs to be looked by the government by providing the same through upgrading existing setup and opening up new government hospitals and investing resources in PHC(primary health centres) and CHC(community health centres) and Tertiary referral centres for the scheme to be truly successful.

By depending only on funding healthcare expenditure through health Insurance may not be a very good idea in the long term unless the government spends more on Public hospitals and improving healthcare infrastructure in the country. Health Insurance financing is an important tool for health care financing but should not be the only tool for developing countries like India. Besides, total subsidization of the scheme with zero contribution from the beneficiaries burdens the finances of the government unnecessarily. A small token payment would have brought a sense of ownership of participants in the scheme. Even the poor are willing to pay if they see value in any scheme. The impact of the scheme can only be evaluated post rollout of the scheme when all variables constraints would come into play, learnings can be had and improvement areas will be discovered by the government.

References

1. IRDAI Welcomes You. (2018). Retrieved from <http://www.irda.gov.in>
2. Home Page: Press Information Bureau. (2018). Retrieved from <http://pib.nic.in>
3. Home Page: Ayushman Bharat. (2018). Retrieved from <http://www.abnhpm.gov.in>
4. Package rates in Ayushman Bharat scheme will put patient safety at stake: IMA. (2018). Retrieved from <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/industry/healthcare/biotech/pharmaceuticals/package-rates-in-ayushman-bharat-scheme-will-put-patient-safety-at-stake-ima/articleshow/64722667.cms>
5. India, & News, I. (2018). Cabinet approves the largest government funded Health Program-Ayushman Bharat National Health Protection Mission (NHPM). Retrieved from <https://www.ibef.org/news/cabinet-approves-the-largest-government-funded-health-program-ayushman-bharat-national-health-protection-mission-nhpm>
6. India's public health system in crisis: Too many patients, not enough doctors. (2018). Retrieved from <https://www.hindustantimes.com/india-news/public-health-system-in-crisis-too-many-patients-not-enough-doctors/story-39XAtFSWGfO0e4qRKcd8fO.html>
7. Karan, A., Yip, W., & Mahal, A. (2017). Extending health insurance to the poor in India: An impact evaluation of Rashtriya Swasthya Bima Yojana on out of pocket spending for healthcare. *Social Science & Medicine (1982)*, 181, 83–92. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2017.03.053>
8. Bakshi, H., Sharma, R., & Kumar, P. (2018). Ayushman Bharat Initiative (2018): What we stand to Gain or Lose! *Indian Journal of Community Medicine : Official Publication of Indian Association of Preventive & Social Medicine*, 43(2), 63–66. http://doi.org/10.4103/ijcm.IJCM_96_18
9. Ravi, S. (2018). The need for reforms in healthcare finance. Retrieved from <https://www.livemint.com/Opinion/HAWtEpMCBhUQSN3jpC5zZM/The-need-for-reforms-in-healthcare-finance.html>
10. India's great healthcare challenge, also an opportunity. (2018). Retrieved from <https://www.hindustantimes.com/india-news/india-s-great-healthcare-challenge-and-opportunity/story-eB691Pj889x57TYo8MobaM.html>